

Hypertension Classification with PPG Bio-signal from the VitalDB Subset of PulseDB: Ensemble Learning

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Abstract

Hypertension affects a large proportion of the global population and is a leading contributor to cardiovascular mortality, yet its detection often relies on cumbersome cuff-based measurements. Photoplethysmography (PPG) offers an affordable, non-invasive alternative, but transforming PPG signals into reliable hypertension classification constitutes major obstacles. This paper addresses a methodological oversight in a prior study on the VitalDB subset of the PulseDB dataset, which attributed visually distinct population average PPG morphologies between healthy and hypertensive segments purely to physiological indicators of hypertension. Through per-subject analysis and Cohen’s d effect-size estimation, this paper demonstrates that these visual differences mainly derive from inter-subject signal variability rather than hypertension-specific morphology, while also showing that population-motivated hand-engineered PPG, VPG, and APG features retain meaningful within-subject discriminative signal. The dataset was processed into three versions via high-correlation and low-variance filtering, random forest feature importance selection, and recursive feature elimination with cross-validation (RFECV). Twelve models — Random Forest, Extremely Randomized Trees, Histogram-based Gradient Boosting, and Logistic Regression across all three dataset versions — were combined into a soft-voting ensemble. The best ensemble achieved a ROC-AUC of 0.891 and a hypertensive-class F1 of 0.57 at an optimized threshold, representing a substantial improvement over the baseline study. These results confirm that population-level morphological features do carry indicators of hypertension, although the signal-to-noise ratio of such features remain low.

1 Introduction

1.1 Hypertension and Photoplethysmography

Hypertension is a cardiovascular disease which affects more than 1 billion adults from 30 years to 79 years globally and is associated with the most common death causes [1]. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), aging, genetics, diet, and lifestyles are main determinants of hypertension. Clinically, there are several levels of elevated blood pressure, with stage 2 hypertension being the most severe [2]. This particular level of the chronic disease is universally defined as having a systolic blood pressure (SBP) higher than 140 mmHg and a diastolic blood pressure (DBP) higher than 90 mmHg. This study focuses on identifying stage 2 hypertension and separating those instances from other cohorts of blood pressure.

Given how pernicious hypertension is, it is therefore crucial to recognize it early. Bio-signals such as electrocardiogram (ECG) and photoplethysmogram (PPG) may provide indications of hypertension and are usually associated with arterial blood pressure (ABP), a bio-signal which tracks blood pressure over time. The advantage of using PPG over ECG is its relatively low cost, ease of use, and convenience [3, 4, 5]. Hence, it is paramount to devise medical pipelines to predict blood pressure from PPG alone to take advantage of all of those beneficial aspects. However, this task proves challenging due to PPG’s method of measuring blood pulses. A photoemitter produces light, which penetrates the patient’s skin, and a photodetector receives the light as waves with varying magnitudes over time due to changes in internal blood volume inducing changes in light intensity [4]. Because it functions through the reflective and absorbing properties of light, factors such as skin tone, external light condition, and motion can introduce significant noise or inaccuracy into the measurement [6]. This necessitates signal processing and machine learning for blood pressure prediction.

1.2 Literature review

The detection of cardiovascular diseases using bio-signals is a popular area of research, which includes the exploration of various bio-signals, the identification of numerous types of diseases, and the experimentation with machine learning or deep learning methods. Generally, these studies can be divided into 2 categories of feature extraction: end-to-end and hand-engineered [7]. The former is characterized by a deep learning approach to automatic feature extraction from raw signals, while the latter involves manually computing features, which are correlated with the target variable, from processed signals.

Previous end-to-end feature extraction pipelines generally include a deep learning neural network capable of identifying spatial and temporal relationships at each point in the signals, bypassing manual feature engineering and allowing models to learn the most relevant representations directly from raw bio-signals. [8] explicitly uses an end-to-end pipeline consisting of a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN), a Long Short-term Memory (LSTM) block, and a dense layer to detect atrial fibrillation from raw PPG data. In a similar approach, [9] trains a CNN, 2 LSTM, and a Multi-layer Perceptron (MLP) sequentially on raw PPG data from the MIMIC-II dataset to predict SBP and DBP. [10] proposes a unique feature extractor-aggregator network to predict cardiac arrest with PPG. [11] and [12] both utilize a generative adversarial network (GAN) to convert raw PPG signals to signals more directly related to blood pressure (ECG and ABP). [3] uses a Transformer-based architecture to predict SBP, DBP, and blood oxygen saturation from raw PPG. [13, 14, 7, 15] all build deep learning architectures of CNN with LSTM or bidirectional LSTM and trained them on raw waveform data. [16] designed a semi-supervised, multi-label architecture trained on raw heart rate data from wearables.

Although these deep learning architectures often yield superior performance, due to their black-box characteristic, their interpretability is often low, preventing widespread adoption in sensitive real-life settings due to low expert confidence [17, 18]. This makes research into manually selected features from processed bio-signals significant. The model presented by [19] extracts 32 processed PPG features, the final matrix reduced from an initial set of 59 features. [20] extracts 46 time-domain and frequency-domain features from PPG signal and performed a search on the best set of features for their final model. [21] computes trend patterns by partitioning data and manually defining features. While [22] and [23] both mention an end-to-end approach, they manually defined approximately 30 additional features for their prediction task. [24] uses an extensive number of ECG attributes for their classification tasks. [25] trains several traditional machine learning models using 4 different processed data channels.

Regarding the processing of PPG signal specifically, several sources provide comprehensive reviews or comparisons of both methodologies. [26, 5] both provide detailed comparisons between conventional machine learning and deep learning methodologies. [27] notes that pulse wave analysis involves processing and manually building the feature matrix, whereas CNN-based architectures can automatically extract those features. [28] summarizes the PPG features commonly associated with blood pressure, aiding future research which includes hand-engineered features.

1.3 Objectives and Structure

[29] asserts the importance of finding a standard feature set which can separate hypertensive patients from healthy patients, citing that while some research has aggregated features associated with blood pressure estimation [28, 27], no universal feature set has been established [5]. However, [29] concludes that finding such a feature set is very difficult due to each dataset’s structural differences. The paper provides evidence from the VitalDB subset of the PulseDB dataset.

However, the means with which the conclusion was reached in [29] had a methodological oversight. That inaccuracy will be explored and addressed in this paper, and an ensemble learning pipeline will be built based on further investigation into the VitalDB subset of the PulseDB dataset.

The following section will provide details about the dataset used in this study, the data preprocessing pipeline implemented, the further examination of the dataset (which addresses the aforementioned oversight), the consequently extracted features, and the 3 distinct data processing pipelines that will become integral to the ensemble learning model. The subsequent section synthesizes and evaluates the results of the machine learning models, providing explanations into their performance. The final section summarizes the paper and recommends directions for future research.

2 Methodology

2.1 Dataset

The overarching dataset, PulseDB, is an aggregation of 2 prominent bio-signal datasets, MIMIC-III and VitalDB, to retrieve all segments which have lead-II ECG, fingertip PPG, and ABP waves. [30]. Any segment without any of the 3 signals was not selected and for each record, the longest recording without any invalid interval was put into the dataset. The MIMIC-III dataset considered in the PulseDB dataset is the intersection subset between the MIMIC-III Waveform dataset and the MIMIC-III Clinical dataset, where only records with both bio-signal and demographic metadata were accepted [31, 32, 33]. The VitalDB dataset contains waveform signals and numerical records of 6,388 patients from the Seoul National University Hospital, which include PPG signal and patients’ SBP and DBP measures. These waveform signals were collected at 500 Hz and the numerical records were recorded at interval of 1-7 seconds [34].

The authors of the PulseDB dataset resampled all waveform signals from VitalDB to 125 Hz to maintain consistency with the MIMIC-III section of the PulseDB dataset [30]. Additionally, they provided a supplementary subset file that contains a compact version of the entire PulseDB dataset, allowing machine learning projects which cannot access the heavy full dataset to be carried out. Due to the resource constraints of this paper, this paper will only utilize the *VitalDB_Train_Subset.mat* file, available on Kaggle as provided by the authors [35], for all of its training and testing purposes. This file contains ECG, PPG, and ABP waveform signals along with the metadata collected for each segment. As PPG is the concern of this paper, it is the only bio-signal used. The SBP and DBP metrics serve as thresholds for the labelling of hypertensive and healthy segments, according to the definition of type 2 hypertension discussed in the Introduction. For the *VitalDB_Train_Subset.mat* file, there were 465,480 segments in total: 360 segments per patient and 1,293 patients [35]. Each segment corresponds to one row in the subsequently built feature matrices.

2.2 Data Preprocessing

Each 10-second segment of PPG signal was resampled from 125 Hz [30] to 100 Hz via polyphase rational-factor resampling. A 3rd-order Butterworth bandpass filter of the pass-band between 0.5 Hz and 8 Hz was then applied. Similar approaches have been implemented in other research [36, 20, 3, 12]. The lower bound ensures that slow-moving average drifts and low-frequency motion artifacts were removed, and the higher bound ensures that high-frequency noise does not pollute the PPG signal. These bounds are within the reasonable range for a PPG signal, although previous research has adopted varied thresholds [5, 36, 37].

A 2nd-order polynomial Savitzky–Golay Smoothing filter with a window length of 11 was used. This further reduces high-frequency noise in each PPG segment, retaining only meaningful physiological information in the waves [38]. Finally, each segment was z-score normalized, which partly removes between-subject absolute amplitude differences while preserving within-subject morphological variation, an important characteristic in the dataset which will be analyzed next. Indeed, this standardization process allows the machine learning models built later to focus on morphological shapes than absolute amplitudes, which are highly influenced by skin tone, slight differences in where the PPG sensor is placed, external light conditions, and other physical states at the time of measurement.

2.3 Population and Subject Average PPG Signal

[29] notes the possibility of finding a set of features that can separate the hypertension class from the healthy class in the VitalDB dataset and attributes this possibility to the clear structural visual differences between the 2 classes’ PPG plot overlays. These plots were constructed by averaging or taking the median of 100 random sample PPG waves from the entire dataset (i.e. the population average or median), 50 for the healthy class and 50 for the hypertension class. Figure 1 shows the population mean PPG wave reported in [29].

The same mean computation can be performed for the VPG signal, the APG signal, and the FFT of PPG frequency-domain plot, illustrated by figures 2, 3, and 4 respectively.

However, concluding that such straightforward discriminant features exist through the population average plots alone would not account for the high variance from the population mean of individual signals, as more clearly seen in the VPG, APG, and Frequency-domain plots – starkly different waves converge to a single

Figure 1: Overlay of 100 PPG segments and a plot of the average wave.

Figure 2: Overlay of 100 VPG segments and a plot of the average wave.

Figure 3: Overlay of 100 APG segments and a plot of the average wave.

Figure 4: Overlay of 100 FFT of PPG segments and a plot of the average wave.

smooth average, yet no waves actually align closely with it. The reason is that considering only the average population signal would fail to eliminate inter-subject differences; it is those vast inter-subject discrepancies that give rise to distinct shapes between the hypertensive segments and the healthy segments. Specifically, upon closer examination of the dataset, 251 of 1293 subjects recorded in the dataset did not exhibit both labels (hypertension/healthy labels were given per segment). Since each subject may have a unique signal shape, these subjects' bio-signals disproportionately influenced or skewed the population mean of either the healthy or the hypertension class, effectively separating them at a population average level. Moreover, since 50 hypertensive segments and 50 healthy segments were randomly sampled, regardless of the identity of the subject (thus included multiple patients), these starkly different PPG signals between subjects made healthy segments and hypertensive segments visually distinct. In other words, these average signals were highly influenced by the identity of the subject rather than purely reflecting hypertension signal indicators.

When a single subject is isolated, several things can be inferred from the inherent structure of the dataset: (1) each subject has a distinct PPG shape, (2) within-subject individual PPG wave variance is significant, and (3) within-subject average waves for hypertension segments and healthy segments are remarkably similar. Figures 5-7 illustrate these points. Points (1) and (3) directly support the idea that the population mean waves are highly influenced by inter-subject differences and by subjects exhibiting a single label: If the average PPG segment for each subject remain uniform across both classes and if the population average PPG segment deviate across those 2 classes, then it would be the difference between the subjects that form this deviation. Point (2) is hidden away when observing the population average PPG wave because when the 100 random PPG waves were averaged, this noise was immediately suppressed.

However, this does not mean the population average PPG waves do not include any indicators of hypertension since it is still possible that, although the signal-to-noise ratio is low due to the intervention of inter-subject difference, features that differentiate between the hypertension class and the healthy class at the population level may do the same at the subject level. The next section will justify this claim and introduce the features extracted for each segment based on the characteristics which separates the hypertension class and the healthy class at the population level.

2.4 Feature Extraction

Table 1 details the hand-engineered features based on the differences between the hypertension and healthy segments in the population average PPG signal.

Figure 5: Overlay of all PPG segments of patient p000001_1, separated by segment class label

Figure 6: Overlay of all PPG segments of patient p000003_1, separated by segment class label

Table 1: Details of extracted features from PPG signal, VPG (1st derivative), and APG (2nd derivative). Per-cycle features are aggregated across all valid cycles within a segment as mean, standard deviation (std), and median, yielding three columns per base feature.

Feature	Definition
PPG Features (mean / std / median) – 27 features	
1–3. $\{mean, std, median\}_{ppg_amp_range}$	Amplitude range of the PPG cycle (peak minus onset value)
4–6. $\{mean, std, median\}_{ppg_peak_amp}$	Systolic peak amplitude
7–9. $\{mean, std, median\}_{ppg_trough_amp}$	Trough amplitude at cycle onset
10–12. $\{mean, std, median\}_{ppg_peak_time}$	Time from cycle onset to systolic peak (s)
13–15. $\{mean, std, median\}_{ppg_peak_fwhm}$	Full width at half maximum of the systolic peak (s). Broader in hypertension, reflecting slower systolic upstroke and downstroke.

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Table 1 – continued from previous page

Feature	Definition
16–18. $\{mean, std, median\}_{ppg_notch_depth}$	Dicrotic notch depth below the systolic peak, normalised by amplitude range. Deeper notch associated with healthy vascular compliance.
19–21. $\{mean, std, median\}_{ppg_diastolic_amp}$	Diastolic bump amplitude above onset, normalised by amplitude range. More pronounced in healthy waveforms.
22–24. $\{mean, std, median\}_{ppg_diastolic_slope}$	Mean slope (linear regression gradient) of the PPG from systolic peak to cycle end (amplitude s^{-1}). Shallower (less negative) in hypertension, indicating slower diastolic decay.
25–27. $\{mean, std, median\}_{ppg_systolic_fraction}$	Normalised timing of the systolic peak within the cycle ($t_{peak}/N_{samples}$). Earlier peak position associated with healthy subjects.
VPG Features (mean / std / median) – 39 features	
28–30. $\{mean, std, median\}_{vpg_amp_range}$	Amplitude range of the VPG cycle
31–33. $\{mean, std, median\}_{vpg_peak_amp}$	Amplitude of the primary (largest) VPG positive peak
34–36. $\{mean, std, median\}_{vpg_peak_time}$	Time of the primary VPG positive peak (s)
37–39. $\{mean, std, median\}_{vpg_2nd_peak_amp}$	Amplitude of the secondary VPG positive peak
40–42. $\{mean, std, median\}_{vpg_2nd_peak_time}$	Time of the secondary VPG positive peak (s)
43–45. $\{mean, std, median\}_{vpg_trough_amp}$	Amplitude of the primary (deepest) VPG trough
46–48. $\{mean, std, median\}_{vpg_trough_time}$	Time of the primary VPG trough (s)
49–51. $\{mean, std, median\}_{vpg_2nd_trough_amp}$	Amplitude of the secondary VPG trough
52–54. $\{mean, std, median\}_{vpg_2nd_trough_time}$	Time of the secondary VPG trough (s)
55–57. $\{mean, std, median\}_{vpg_crosses_zero}$	Binary indicator: 1 if the VPG crosses zero within the cycle, 0 otherwise
58–60. $\{mean, std, median\}_{vpg_peak_fwhm}$	Full width at half maximum of the primary VPG positive peak (s). Broader in hypertension, reflecting slower blood acceleration.
61–63. $\{mean, std, median\}_{vpg_trough_peak_ratio}$	$ vpg_trough_amp /vpg_peak_amp$ — asymmetry between the acceleration and deceleration phases. Larger ratio (sharper deceleration) associated with healthy subjects.
64–66. $\{mean, std, median\}_{vpg_zero_cross_after_trough}$	Time (s) from the primary VPG trough to the subsequent zero crossing. Shorter recovery time associated with healthy, more compliant arteries.
APG Features (mean / std / median) – 39 features	
67–69. $\{mean, std, median\}_{apg_amp_range}$	Amplitude range of the APG cycle
70–72. $\{mean, std, median\}_{apg_peak_amp}$	Amplitude of the primary (largest) APG positive peak (wave <i>a</i>)
73–75. $\{mean, std, median\}_{apg_peak_time}$	Time of the primary APG positive peak (s)
76–78. $\{mean, std, median\}_{apg_2nd_peak_amp}$	Amplitude of the secondary APG positive peak
79–81. $\{mean, std, median\}_{apg_2nd_peak_time}$	Time of the secondary APG positive peak (s)
82–84. $\{mean, std, median\}_{apg_trough_amp}$	Amplitude of the primary (deepest) APG trough (wave <i>b</i>)
85–87. $\{mean, std, median\}_{apg_trough_time}$	Time of the primary APG trough (s)
88–90. $\{mean, std, median\}_{apg_2nd_trough_amp}$	Amplitude of the secondary APG trough
91–93. $\{mean, std, median\}_{apg_2nd_trough_time}$	Time of the secondary APG trough (s)
94–96. $\{mean, std, median\}_{apg_b_a_gap}$	$apg_peak_amp - apg_trough_amp $ — raw amplitude gap between the <i>a</i> wave (early systolic positive) and <i>b</i> wave (early systolic negative). Larger gap associated with healthy, more compliant vessels.
97–99. $\{mean, std, median\}_{apg_2nd_peak_ratio}$	$apg_2nd_peak_amp/apg_peak_amp$ — relative height of the diastolic APG hump. More prominent (larger ratio) in hypertension, reflecting increased reflected wave amplitude.

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Feature	Definition
100–102. $\{mean, std, median\}_{apg_2nd_peak_latency}$	$apg_2nd_peak_time/cycle_duration$ — normalised timing of the secondary APG peak. Later reflected wave associated with hypertension.
103–105. $\{mean, std, median\}_{apg_trough_fwhm}$	Full width at half minimum of the primary APG trough (s). Broader trough associated with reduced vascular compliance in hypertension.
Segment-Level FFT Features – 4 features	
<i>Computed once per segment on the full normalised PPG signal; not aggregated across cycles.</i>	
106. $fft_h2_h1_ratio$	Magnitude of the 2 nd harmonic relative to the fundamental. Higher ratio associated with healthy waveforms, indicating richer harmonic content.
107. $fft_h3_h1_ratio$	Magnitude of the 3 rd harmonic relative to the fundamental. Higher ratio associated with healthy, sharper waveform morphology.
108. $fft_fundamental_bw$	Bandwidth of the fundamental spectral peak at the –3 dB (half-power) point (Hz). Wider bandwidth indicates greater heart-rate variability, associated with hypertension.
109. $fft_high_freq_ratio$	Ratio of spectral power above 4 Hz to total power. Higher ratio associated with sharper, healthier waveforms.
Quality Control Metadata – 2 features (excluded from model training)	
110. $valid_cycle_count$	Number of valid cardiac cycles retained after length-based quality filtering
111. $cycle_rejection_rate$	Proportion of detected cycles rejected by the quality filter

Quantifying whether these population-motivated features actually hold value in hypertension classification requires grouping all segments together by subject. This removes any inter-subject variation when these segments are processed. Next, each subject’s segments are separated into 2 additional groups based on their labels: hypertension or healthy. From there, Cohen’s d values were computed: this measures how much each feature differs between that subject’s own healthy segments and their own hypertensive segments, normalized by that subject’s own within-state variability. Figure 8 shows the top 20 features with high absolute d scores. Green bars indicate that these features are generally higher in hypertension labelled segments and red bars vice versa. The standard deviation (SD) metric shows the magnitude of this difference. Hence, according to Cohen’s d analysis, these features, although previously proven to be dominated by inter-subject discrepancies at the population average level, can still potentially separate between hypertensive and healthy segments. In other words, the population average PPG plots showed both inter-subject differences and slight indications of hypertension rather than just the former.

2.5 Data Cleaning and Transformation

2.5.1 Baseline Processing – version 1 of dataset

The first version of the dataset is cleaned with column dropping, imputation, correlation-based reduction, variance-based reduction, Winsorization, Power Transform, and Robust Scaling.

First, features $valid_cycle_count$ and $cycle_rejection_rate$ do not take part in the machine learning training process, so they are dropped – their primary function was to validate the quality of each segment depending on their individual cycles. Train-test split was subsequently performed, but unlike [29], the IDs of subjects were accounted for, such that each subject was either part of the training set or testing set, not both. This ensures that information about a subject is not leaked into training and prevents the model from learning subject identity, forcing it to learn a mapping from PPG to hypertension instead. Afterwards, median values for each feature per class was imputed into missing data placeholders. It is important that this step and subsequent data transformation steps were done after train-test split as to not allow data leakage.

Then, correlation-based filtering was applied to the features to automatically drop one feature out of each pair which manifested a correlation of more than 0.9 in absolute scale, removing 52 correlated features. Features with low variance (variance < 0.01) were also dropped because low variance indicated no significant difference between the hypertension class and the healthy class, leaving 33 remaining features, not including the label.

Figure 7: Overlay of all PPG segments of patient p000005_1, separated by segment class label

To remove outliers that are not meaningful physiological values, Winsorization was applied. Skewness was also accounted for through Yeo-Johnson Power Transformation. Finally, Robust Scaling was applied because it is more resistant to outliers.

2.5.2 Feature-Importance-based Processing – version 2 of dataset

The second version of the dataset was derived by considering a preliminary random forest (RF) model’s distribution of feature importance. Similar to the first version, *valid_cycle_count* and *cycle_rejection_rate* were dropped before subject-wise train-test split was performed. Per-class median imputation of missing data followed and importance filtering was done. In the latter step, features of high value in the simple RF’s decision, hence contributing to the model’s Receiver Operating Characteristic - Area Under the Curve (ROC-AUC) metric, were kept while those with importance figures below 0.001 were dropped. 17 remaining features of the original 109 were dropped, and 7 features were removed through correlation and variance filtering with the same thresholds as the previous trial. Winsorization, Power Transform, and Robust Scaling were also similarly applied.

2.5.3 RFECV-based Processing – version 3 of dataset

The third version of the dataset was derived by performing Recursive Feature Elimination with Cross-Validation (RFECV) following similar processes of dropping *valid_cycle_count* and *cycle_rejection_rate*, subject-aware train-test split, median imputation, Winsorization, Power Transform, and Robust Scaling. RFECV was ran on a 20% stratified subsample (with shuffling, step of 1, and using ROC-AUC as scoring metric) and a simple RF (100 decision trees, minimum samples in leaf of 5, and class-weighted) enough to distinguish signal from noise. The pipeline only removed 5 out of 109 features, however. Further processing will be done if needed to boost model performance in the Machine Learning stage.

2.6 Machine Learning and Results

For all models to be built, class weights were first computed to account for class imbalance in the dataset. Table 2 summarizes the distribution of healthy and hypertensive segments across the training and testing subsets for each of the 3 cleaned versions of the dataset.

Figure 8: Top 20 features with high absolute d scores

Table 2: Distribution of healthy and hypertensive segments across training and testing subsets

Class	Training Subset	Testing Subset	Total Records
Healthy	404,097	12,332	416,429
Hypertensive	47,338	1,708	49,046
Total	451,435	14,040	465,475

2.6.1 Random Forest Models

For each version of the dataset, a RF with 300 decision trees, no specified max depth, and a minimum of 5 samples per leaf node was trained. Because many features held negative permutation importance in the initial fit – introducing noise to the classification task – all negative-importance features were subsequently dropped and the RF was retrained on the filtered feature set. This two-step pipeline was applied identically to trials 1, 2, and 3. Table 3 summarizes the post-filter performance across all three trials.

Table 3: Random forest performance on hypertension classification (post-filter, all trials)

Trial	Bal. Acc.	ROC-AUC	F1 (Hyp.)	Recall (Hyp.)	Prec. (Hyp.)	Accuracy
Trial 1	0.718	0.882	0.54	0.48	0.62	0.900
Trial 2	0.722	0.881	0.55	0.48	0.63	0.900
Trial 3	0.717	0.892	0.56	0.46	0.70	0.910

2.6.2 Extra Models for Ensemble

For each cleaned version of the dataset (trials 1, 2, and 3), an Extremely Randomized Trees (ExtraTrees) model was built (300 trees, minimum samples in leaf of 5). Similar to RFs, ExtraTrees are ensemble methods, but instead of choosing optimal decision thresholds for individual trees, ExtraTrees randomize these thresholds. Therefore, they deal better with noise than RFs theoretically. Including them in the final ensemble model should boost the model’s ability to tolerate noise. Table 4 records the performance of the ExtraTrees models across all three trial datasets.

Table 4: Extra Trees performance on hypertension classification (all trials)

Trial	Bal. Acc.	ROC-AUC	F1 (Hyp.)	Recall (Hyp.)	Prec. (Hyp.)	Accuracy
Trial 1	0.739	0.851	0.49	0.59	0.43	0.850
Trial 2	0.765	0.880	0.52	0.65	0.43	0.850
Trial 3	0.750	0.884	0.55	0.57	0.53	0.890

Histogram-based Gradient Boosting Classification Trees (HGBT) were trained on each trial’s dataset. Originally, the intended models to train were Gradient Boosting, but since each version’s dataset was very large, the process was very slow. Therefore, the HGBT algorithm (maximum sequential trees built of 300, learning rate of 0.05, max depth of 4) was used as a replacement. Table 5 records the performance of the HGBT models across all three trial datasets.

Table 5: HGBT performance on hypertension classification (all trials)

Trial	Bal. Acc.	ROC-AUC	F1 (Hyp.)	Recall (Hyp.)	Prec. (Hyp.)	Accuracy
Trial 1	0.778	0.884	0.45	0.81	0.31	0.760
Trial 2	0.778	0.887	0.45	0.80	0.31	0.760
Trial 3	0.794	0.897	0.47	0.82	0.33	0.770

Finally, Logistic Regression models (L2 regularization, LIBLINEAR solver, regularization strength of 10, maximum iterations of 1000) were trained on each version of the dataset, diversifying the models which take part in the final ensemble. Table 6 records the performance of the Logistic Regression models across all three trial datasets.

Table 6: Logistic regression performance on hypertension classification (all trials)

Trial	Bal. Acc.	ROC-AUC	F1 (Hyp.)	Recall (Hyp.)	Prec. (Hyp.)	Accuracy
Trial 1	0.721	0.798	0.38	0.76	0.25	0.700
Trial 2	0.726	0.804	0.39	0.73	0.27	0.730
Trial 3	0.729	0.813	0.39	0.75	0.26	0.710

2.6.3 Ensemble Learning

The final ensemble includes 12 models: 3 RFs, 3 ExtraTrees, 3 HGBT, and 3 Logistic Regression (each of the 4 types of models belongs to a version of the dataset). The ensemble is a soft-voting ensemble, where each model’s prediction is weighted with its class probability. 3 methods of building the final ensemble were used: simple average, threshold sweep on simple average, and ROC-AUC weighted average.

The first approach (simple average) takes the raw predicted probabilities from all 12 models and averages them with equal weight (each model contributes 1/12). A segment is classified as hypertensive if this average probability

exceeds 0.50 (threshold = 0.5). No model is considered more reliable than any other. The performance of this method’s ensemble is displayed in table 7.

Table 7: Soft-voting ensemble performance (simple average, threshold = 0.50)

Class/Metric	Precision	Recall	F1-Score	Support
Healthy	0.95	0.89	0.92	12,332
Hypertensive	0.45	0.67	0.54	1,708
Macro Average	0.70	0.78	0.73	–
Weighted Average	0.89	0.86	0.87	–
<i>Additional Metrics</i>				
Overall Accuracy	0.860			
Balanced Accuracy	0.777			
ROC-AUC Score	0.891			

The second approach (threshold sweep on simple average) involves the same averaged sum described in the first approach, but rather than classifying based on a threshold of 0.5, it searches across possible thresholds from 0.25 to 0.65 with a step of 0.01 to find the one which maximizes the minority class’ F1-score. The performance of this method’s ensemble is displayed in table 8.

Table 8: Soft-voting ensemble performance (simple average, threshold = 0.62)

Class/Metric	Precision	Recall	F1-Score	Support
Healthy	0.94	0.95	0.94	12,332
Hypertensive	0.61	0.53	0.57	1,708
Macro Average	0.77	0.74	0.76	–
Weighted Average	0.90	0.90	0.90	–
<i>Additional Metrics</i>				
Overall Accuracy	0.900			
Balanced Accuracy	0.743			
ROC-AUC Score	0.891			

The third approach (ROC-AUC weighted average) considers each model’s ROC-AUC score when calculating its weight in the ensemble rather than distributing the weight uniformly as previously done. Table 9 summarizes each model’s ROC-AUC score and its corresponding normalized weight.

Table 9: Per-model ROC-AUC scores and normalised ensemble weights for the AUC-weighted soft-voting ensemble

Model	Trial	ROC-AUC	Ensemble Weight
Random Forest	Trial 1	0.8820	0.0852
Random Forest	Trial 2	0.8805	0.0850
Random Forest	Trial 3	0.8924	0.0862
Extra Trees	Trial 1	0.8513	0.0822
Extra Trees	Trial 2	0.8802	0.0850
Extra Trees	Trial 3	0.8840	0.0854
Hist. Gradient Boosting	Trial 1	0.8842	0.0854
Hist. Gradient Boosting	Trial 2	0.8872	0.0857
Hist. Gradient Boosting	Trial 3	0.8965	0.0866
Logistic Regression	Trial 1	0.7984	0.0771
Logistic Regression	Trial 2	0.8042	0.0777
Logistic Regression	Trial 3	0.8128	0.0785

That final approach accounts for each model’s individual performance: a better model should have a larger significance in the final decision-making process of the overarching ensemble model. Table 10 directly compares the threshold-unadjusted performance of the equal-weight (first ensemble approach) and AUC-weighted ensemble variants, showing the marginal effect of AUC-weighting at the default threshold.

Table 10: Comparison of equal-weight and AUC-weighted ensemble at threshold = 0.50

Weighting	Bal. Acc.	ROC-AUC	F1 (Hyp.)	Recall (Hyp.)	Prec. (Hyp.)
Equal weights	0.777	0.891	0.54	0.67	0.45
AUC-weighted	0.776	0.891	0.54	0.67	0.45

To boost the performance of the AUC-weighted ensemble, threshold sweeping was applied using the same procedure described for the simple average ensemble. The threshold-adjusted ensemble’s performance is summarized in table 11.

Table 11: Soft-voting ensemble performance (AUC-weighted average, threshold = 0.59)

Class/Metric	Precision	Recall	F1-Score	Support
Healthy	0.94	0.94	0.94	12,332
Hypertensive	0.57	0.56	0.57	1,708
Macro Average	0.76	0.75	0.75	–
Weighted Average	0.89	0.90	0.90	–
<i>Additional Metrics</i>				
Overall Accuracy	0.900			
Balanced Accuracy	0.751			
ROC-AUC Score	0.891			

3 Evaluation

Table 12 summarizes the performance of all models trained in this study. Overall, the best model in terms of accuracy and recall is the HGBT trained on the third trial, where the dataset was processed via RFECV. However, its especially low precision drags its F1 score down, implying that the model is too aggressive in classifying an instance as hypertensive. Therefore, although the ensemble models scored slightly lower in balanced accuracy and ROC-AUC,

they exhibit a more balanced Recall-Precision distribution, hence the relatively higher F1 scores. Importantly, these ensemble methods achieved a high ROC-AUC while not suffering extreme skew between Recall and Precision.

While at the default threshold (0.50), the ensemble methods achieved relatively similar performance, after threshold sweeping was implemented, they traded in balanced accuracy for a higher F1 score, suggesting a balance between Recall and Precision.

Regarding the same metrics for the majority (healthy) class, each ensemble model yielded high performance, with F1 scores greater than 0.90.

These models are a significant improvement from those reported in [29], suggesting that discriminant features at the population average level also exhibit similar, albeit subtler, characteristics for separating healthy and hypertensive segments. Nevertheless, these models have not yet achieved satisfactory performance for hypertension detection.

For a medical disease prediction task, a higher recall is arguably more important than a higher precision. Whereas low precision may consume more resources due to medical examination, diagnosis, and prevention (a low-precision model would incorrectly flag a healthy patient as hypertensive, encouraging them to undergo such processes), a low recall would risk the safety of the patient (a low-recall model would faultily leave diseases undetected).

Another notable detail is that the dataset, for all 3 trials, was most likely nonlinear. While logistic regression, an inherently linear model, achieved low precision, tree-based models performed better because these models can adapt to this nonlinearity. Nevertheless, aggregating all models into an ensemble allows the final model to generalize better, achieving a higher F1 score on average, suggesting better balance between recall and precision.

Table 12: Summary of all models and ensemble variants on the hypertension classification task

Model	Trial	Balanced Acc.	ROC-AUC	F1 (Hyp.)	Recall (Hyp.)	Precision (Hyp.)
<i>Random Forest</i>						
RF	Trial 1	0.718	0.882	0.538	0.476	0.618
RF	Trial 2	0.722	0.881	0.547	0.483	0.630
RF	Trial 3	0.717	0.892	0.557	0.461	0.702
<i>Extra Trees</i>						
Extra Trees	Trial 1	0.739	0.851	0.494	0.588	0.425
Extra Trees	Trial 2	0.765	0.880	0.519	0.647	0.434
Extra Trees	Trial 3	0.750	0.884	0.551	0.569	0.534
<i>Histogram-based Gradient Boosting</i>						
HistGradBoost	Trial 1	0.778	0.884	0.447	0.805	0.310
HistGradBoost	Trial 2	0.778	0.887	0.449	0.800	0.312
HistGradBoost	Trial 3	0.794	0.897	0.467	0.823	0.326
<i>Logistic Regression</i>						
Logistic Regression	Trial 1	0.721	0.798	0.376	0.756	0.251
Logistic Regression	Trial 2	0.726	0.804	0.392	0.726	0.268
Logistic Regression	Trial 3	0.729	0.813	0.388	0.754	0.261
<i>Soft-Voting Ensemble (12 models)</i>						
Equal weights	$t = 0.50$	0.777	0.891	0.535	0.667	0.447
Equal weights	$t = 0.62$	0.743	0.891	0.568	0.533	0.607
AUC-weighted	$t = 0.50$	0.776	0.891	0.536	0.665	0.449
AUC-weighted	$t = 0.59$	0.751	0.891	0.566	0.559	0.574

4 Conclusion

This paper addressed a methodological oversight of the interpretation of the VitalDB subset of the PulseDB dataset in [29]. It pointed out that the visually dissimilar shapes of the healthy and hypertensive segments were not due to pure indications of hypertension. Instead, it most likely emerged because of between-subject differences when 100 PPG segments were randomly selected, as supported by the fact that per patient, the average of all segments across the 2 classes was nearly inseparable, and that between each patient, their PPG signals varied significantly. However, by performing Cohen’s d analysis, some features which separated the 2 classes at the population average level could also separate the 2 classes at the subject level.

The dataset was processed into three versions to allow the final ensembles to capture diversity with the same set of models, improving generalizability. 3 RFs, ExtraTrees, HGBT, and Logistic Regression models were trained. The HGBT model for trial 3 did relatively well overall but did not balance precision with recall, a limitation mitigated

by the ensemble models.

The final models yielded significantly better performance than both trials of [29], which is consistent with the conclusion reached in that study and which suggests that features that separated the classes at the population average level held some signal towards hypertension classification. Nevertheless, compared to research utilizing the more standard MIMIC-III dataset, the ensemble models built still performed relatively poorly [13, 9, 3, 20], suggesting that the signal-to-noise ratio of these features is low.

Therefore, future research should focus on determining more discriminant features for the VitalDB subset of the PulseDB dataset and building models which perform better at classifying hypertensive segments. An alternative approach would be to build regression models, instead of classification models, to predict SBP and DBP values and apply a threshold based on the definition of hypertension. Moreover, as noted in the Dataset section, studies with more physical resource may include more data beyond the compact subset used in this study.

References

- [1] “Hypertension.” <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/hypertension>.
- [2] “Why is Hypertension a Silent Killer?.” <https://my.clevelandclinic.org/health/diseases/4314-hypertension-high-blood-pressure>.
- [3] Y. Chu, K. Tang, Y.-C. Hsu, T. Huang, D. Wang, W. Li, S. I. Savitz, X. Jiang, and S. Shams, “Non-invasive arterial blood pressure measurement and SpO₂ estimation using PPG signal: A deep learning framework,” *BMC Medical Informatics and Decision Making*, vol. 23, p. 131, July 2023.
- [4] K. B. Kim and H. J. Baek, “Photoplethysmography in Wearable Devices: A Comprehensive Review of Technological Advances, Current Challenges, and Future Directions,” *Electronics*, vol. 12, p. 2923, July 2023.
- [5] E. Mejía-Mejía, J. Allen, K. Budidha, C. El-Hajji, P. A. Kyriacou, and P. H. Charlton, “Photoplethysmography signal processing and synthesis,” in *Photoplethysmography*, pp. 69–146, Elsevier, 2022.
- [6] S. C. M.Sc, “Photoplethysmography (PPG).” [https://www.news-medical.net/health/Photoplethysmography-\(PPG\).aspx](https://www.news-medical.net/health/Photoplethysmography-(PPG).aspx), July 2016.
- [7] H. Mohammadi, B. Tarvirdizadeh, K. Alipour, and M. Ghamari, “Cuff-less blood pressure monitoring via PPG signals using a hybrid CNN-BiLSTM deep learning model with attention mechanism,” *Scientific Reports*, vol. 15, p. 22229, July 2025.
- [8] I. Gotlibovych, S. Crawford, D. Goyal, J. Liu, Y. Kerem, D. Benaron, D. Yilmaz, G. Marcus, and Y. Li, “End-to-end Deep Learning from Raw Sensor Data: Atrial Fibrillation Detection using Wearables,” 2018.
- [9] A. Tazarv and M. Levorato, “A Deep Learning Approach to Predict Blood Pressure from PPG Signals,” July 2021.
- [10] S. Kataria, R. Xiao, T. Ruchti, M. Clark, J. Lu, R. J. Lee, J. Grunwell, and X. Hu, “Continuous Cardiac Arrest Prediction in ICU using PPG Foundation Model,” Feb. 2025.
- [11] E. Brophy, M. De Vos, G. Boylan, and T. Ward, “Estimation of Continuous Blood Pressure from PPG via a Federated Learning Approach,” *Sensors*, vol. 21, p. 6311, Sept. 2021.
- [12] P. Sarkar and A. Etemad, “CardioGAN: Attentive Generative Adversarial Network with Dual Discriminators for Synthesis of ECG from PPG,” Dec. 2020.
- [13] N. Q. Mahardika T, Y. N. Fuadah, D. U. Jeong, and K. M. Lim, “PPG Signals-Based Blood-Pressure Estimation Using Grid Search in Hyperparameter Optimization of CNN–LSTM,” *Diagnostics*, vol. 13, p. 2566, Aug. 2023.
- [14] R. S. Alkhalwaldeh, B. Al-Ahmad, A. Ksibi, N. Ghatasheh, E. M. Abu-Taieh, G. Aldehim, M. Ayadi, and S. M. Alkhalwaldeh, “Convolution Neural Network Bidirectional Long Short-Term Memory for Heartbeat Arrhythmia Classification,” *International Journal of Computational Intelligence Systems*, vol. 16, p. 197, Dec. 2023.
- [15] Y.-A. Choi, S.-J. Park, J.-A. Jun, C.-S. Pyo, K.-H. Cho, H.-S. Lee, and J.-H. Yu, “Deep Learning-Based Stroke Disease Prediction System Using Real-Time Bio Signals,” *Sensors*, vol. 21, p. 4269, June 2021.
- [16] B. Ballinger, J. Hsieh, A. Singh, N. Sohoni, J. Wang, G. H. Tison, G. M. Marcus, J. M. Sanchez, C. Maguire, J. E. Olgin, and M. J. Pletcher, “DeepHeart: Semi-Supervised Sequence Learning for Cardiovascular Risk Prediction,” 2018.
- [17] M. S. Islam, I. Hussain, M. M. Rahman, S. J. Park, and M. A. Hossain, “Explainable Artificial Intelligence Model for Stroke Prediction Using EEG Signal,” *Sensors*, vol. 22, p. 9859, Dec. 2022.
- [18] J. Chu, W.-T. Yang, Y.-T. Chang, and F.-L. Yang, “Visual Reassessment with Flux-Interval Plot Configuration after Automatic Classification for Accurate Atrial Fibrillation Detection by Photoplethysmography,” *Diagnostics*, vol. 12, p. 1304, May 2022.
- [19] Y.-C. Hsu, Y.-H. Li, C.-C. Chang, and L. N. Harfiya, “Generalized Deep Neural Network Model for Cuffless Blood Pressure Estimation with Photoplethysmogram Signal Only,” *Sensors*, vol. 20, p. 5668, Oct. 2020.
- [20] A. Nishan, S. M. Taslim Uddin Raju, M. I. Hossain, S. A. Dipto, S. M. Tanvir Uddin, A. Sijan, M. A. S. Chowdhury, A. Ahmad, and M. Mahamudul Hasan Khan, “A continuous cuffless blood pressure measurement from optimal PPG characteristic features using machine learning algorithms,” *Heliyon*, vol. 10, p. e27779, Mar. 2024.
- [21] Q. Zhang, “Acute ischaemic stroke prediction from physiological time series patterns,” *Australasian Medical Journal*, vol. 6, pp. 280–286, June 2013.
- [22] J. Yu, S. Park, S.-H. Kwon, K.-H. Cho, and H. Lee, “AI-Based Stroke Disease Prediction System Using ECG and PPG Bio-Signals,” *IEEE Access*, vol. 10, pp. 43623–43638, 2022.

- [23] J. Yu, S. Park, S.-H. Kwon, C. M. B. Ho, C.-S. Pyo, and H. Lee, "AI-Based Stroke Disease Prediction System Using Real-Time Electromyography Signals," *Applied Sciences*, vol. 10, p. 6791, Sept. 2020.
- [24] S. R. Tithi, A. Aktar, F. Aleem, and A. Chakrabarty, "ECG data analysis and heart disease prediction using machine learning algorithms," in *2019 IEEE Region 10 Symposium (TENSymp)*, (Kolkata, India), pp. 819–824, IEEE, June 2019.
- [25] A. Hannan, S. M. Cheema, and I. M. Pires, "Machine learning-based smart wearable system for cardiac arrest monitoring using hybrid computing," *Biomedical Signal Processing and Control*, vol. 87, p. 105519, Jan. 2024.
- [26] Y. J. Lee, C. Park, H. Kim, S. J. Cho, and W.-H. Yeo, "Artificial intelligence on biomedical signals: Technologies, applications, and future directions," *Med-X*, vol. 2, p. 25, Dec. 2024.
- [27] L. Frey, C. Menon, and M. Elgendi, "Blood pressure measurement using only a smartphone," *npj Digital Medicine*, vol. 5, p. 86, July 2022.
- [28] M. Elgendi, E. Jost, A. Alian, R. R. Fletcher, H. Bomberg, U. Eichenberger, and C. Menon, "Photoplethysmography Features Correlated with Blood Pressure Changes," *Diagnostics*, vol. 14, p. 2309, Oct. 2024.
- [29] U. Nguyen, "On the Limitations of Hand-Engineered PPG Features for Hypertension Classification: Evidence from the VitalDB Subset of PulseDB," Mar. 2026.
- [30] W. Wang, P. Mohseni, K. L. Kilgore, and L. Najafzadeh, "PulseDB: A large, cleaned dataset based on MIMIC-III and VitalDB for benchmarking cuff-less blood pressure estimation methods," *Frontiers in Digital Health*, vol. 4, p. 1090854, Feb. 2023.
- [31] B. Moody, G. Moody, M. Villarroel, G. Clifford, and I. Silva, "MIMIC-III Waveform Database Matched Subset," 2017.
- [32] B. Moody, G. Moody, M. Villarroel, G. Clifford, and I. Silva, "MIMIC-III Waveform Database," 2017.
- [33] A. Johnson, T. Pollard, and R. Mark, "MIMIC-III Clinical Database," 2015.
- [34] H.-C. Lee and C.-W. Jung, "VitalDB, a high-fidelity multi-parameter vital signs database in surgical patients."
- [35] Weinan Wang, "PulseDB-Balanced-Training-and-Testing."
- [36] D. Pollreisz and N. TaheriNejad, "Detection and Removal of Motion Artifacts in PPG Signals," *Mobile Networks and Applications*, vol. 27, pp. 728–738, Apr. 2022.
- [37] S. Bagha and L. Shaw, "A Real Time Analysis of PPG Signal for Measurement of SpO2 and Pulse Rate," *International Journal of Computer Applications*, vol. 36, pp. 45–50, Dec. 2011.
- [38] P. A. Gorry, "General least-squares smoothing and differentiation by the convolution (Savitzky-Golay) method," *Analytical Chemistry*, vol. 62, pp. 570–573, Mar. 1990.